

Peoples' Governance Forum

DIGALA RAGHAVARAJU, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, raghava.digala@gmail.com

BALAJI SUNIL CHANDRA, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, hod.cse@svitatp.ac.in

JANGILI RAVI KISHORE, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, jangiliravi.kishore1@gmail.com

Department of CSE, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology, N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu,
Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract

This report describes the developmental stages of the cyberpolicing organization, Peoples' Governance Forum which came into being in 2017 in cooperation with PAIRS foundation. Our practical case study of cyberpolicing gave birth to PGF's cyber intelligence alternatives to defuse the cybercrimes. In this context, in-order-to induce the cyber ethics into the students, negate the national cognitive impairment and reverse engineer it by inculcating the national values into them, PGF members provided advice and counselling to students. We know that highly trained, skilled, and devoted instructors in the academic institutions are quite crucial for national growth along with attaining the educational objectives. In raising the awareness among the pupils about the online ethics, instructors are the main agents. The senior professors at JNTUH affiliated colleges are listed as PGF members. The PGF founder believed in cyberpolicing via R&D pushing the Ph.D scholar members of PGF to strive for the improved QoDNL (Quality of digital national life). Its other members are students pursuing Master's, Bachelor's, or Advanced degrees in technology, computer science, mathematics, or political science. Without seeking any personal gain, its members took on the national duty of educating students about the need of responsible internet usage in the hopes that some of them would engage in cybercrime.

We give some supporting snapshots of the websites of selected PGF researchers and our research and development accomplishments to emphasise the qualities of the PGF's performance for national development.

Keywords: *Peoples' Governance Forum, Quality of digital national life (QoDNL), Cyberpolicing, Cybercrimes*

1. Introduction

The victims of financial technology cybercrimes are the people whose money is at risk. But what about sedition cybercrimes perpetrated by TBDCOs that face financial losses? Tell me who has been hurt. In this case, no one can be considered a victim. The country is suffering. The identity of the digital country is in shambles. Then who would try to justify themselves by filing a lawsuit? Despite the rise of cybercrime, cyberpolicing has not kept pace. Here, care for nation building takes the stage. Nation built by students. Therefore, they need to be directed and counselled in the right direction so that they may internalise the many facets of Indian nationalism, including but not limited to: Mother India Consciousness, national unity, national solidarity, national sovereignty, and national amity. In order to help students improve their cyber ethics and create a safer digital India, PGF's founder, Dr. K. Chandra Sekharaiah, a professor at JNTUH who has received training from the Indian military at the Officers Training Academy in Nagpur and the Air

Force Administrative College in Coimbatore, established a cyberpolicing thinktank. Improving the QoDNL (Quality of digital national life) is its primary goal. This is a forum for raising awareness and providing services to address problems.

2. Background

It was noticed by a group of persons who are now PGF members that JNTUJAC maintained a webpage. This website/organization is implicated in four cybercrimes harming the country as well as state. 1. State Emblem of India (Prohibition of Improper Use) Act 2005 violation, 2. Sedition Law violation, 3. Cheating the Nation crime and 4. Identity Theft crime. For any criminality to be found, cyber forensics plays key part and here in our case study the earlier works of R&D demonstrate how a web crawler tool, the internet archive wayback machine is utilised to take the snapshots of websites or webpages online. Around 2500 registrations were made on this website. The registrants were the academics, professors, Ph.D researchers separate from postgraduate and undergraduate students. If the educated elite and instructors have fell victim to such cybercriminal groups who country-abusive, then who is to preserve that nation. The Peoples' Governance Forum has consequently developed to reduce the harmful impacts of the cybercrimes conducted by TBDCOs (Triple Big Data Cybercriminal organizations - FGoT, FGoI, JNTUJAC) and detonate them.

3. Cyberpolicing through R&D

The cyberpolicing through R&D methodology is to transform ill-informed society to well-informed society, regressive/cybercriminal society to progressive society and promote the quality of digital national life. The PGF webdevices are produced by the PGF's R&D chief and the research scholar members of PGF to generate awareness among the students and other people to keep away from such cybercrimes. Samples of these are discussed below along with the screenshots.

- A. As seen in figure1, PGF was originally a website when it was launched. This website may be accessed online at this URL:
<https://sites.google.com/site/sekharaiiahk/apeoples-governanceforumwebpage>. As seen in figure2, a subsequent web device was created with the URL <https://sites.google.com/site/chandraksekharaiiah/pgf-pairsf>. You may find Dr. K. Chandra Sekharaiiah's social media profiles on these webdevices: Soundcloud, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and Google+.

Figure1: The screenshot of initial webpage of the

Peoples' Governance forum.

B. Sri. N. Srihari Rao created a web device (<https://sites.google.com/view/nsraopgf>) that includes all the research publications and presentations from the whole cyberpolicing case study <https://sites.google.com/view/nsraopgf/home/researchpublications/whole-cyberpolicing-case-study-related-research-publications-in-our-rg>). Here you can find a table that lists all of the research papers that were consulted for our cyberpolicing case study. You can also find links to download the papers as well as links to YouTube videos that accompany them. Accordingly, the table had 30 papers, 60 of which had download links, and 35 of which had YouTube connections. To see his video presentations, visit his YouTube channel at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdtbHk9FJ5ixc0sFoapfeow/videos>. Images of several RTI petitions and replies may be seen on one page of the website. In order to create an academic climate that discourages future cybercrimes similar to the one described in the case study, the website's homepage invites site visitors to offer critical analysis of the case study as pabulum, or ideas that induce or provoke thought. As an additional technique to encourage students to develop a sense of national pride and unity, it asks for critical remarks outlining five to ten strategies for moving beyond the trauma of abuse.

Figure2: The web device of the PGF's R&D chief for Peoples' Governance forum.

Figure3: Screenshot of PGF's Web device developed by the PGF member N. Srihari Rao.

- C. Another web device developed by Sri. Ravi Kumar is <http://sites.google.com/view/pgfsrk>. His research publications w.r.t the cyberpolicing case study is shown in the figure4. It included the menu items as RTI documents, Analysis of case study and Research publications.

Figure4: The image of a webpage of the web device developed by Sri. Ravi Kumar.

- D. Sri A. Ramesh Babu as a PGF member developed his own PGF webdevice for the awareness generation. Its URL is <https://sites.google.com/view/jrbpgfwebsite/home> shown in the figure below.

Figure5: Screenshot of PGF web device developed by Sri. Ramesh babu, a member of PGF and senior faculty in JNTUH affiliated college

- E. Another web device developed by B. Malathi, a PGF member and Research scholar is shown in the figure6. The PGF print media is available on its webpage url <https://sites.google.com/view/peoplesgovernanceforum/development-milestones#h.874mklghj89n>. This web device includes the following:
- i. Manifesto of PGF,

- ii. Background of the cyber policing case study,
- iii. Functional Approach with the research publications of the owner of the web device and research publications related to the cyberpolicing case study by the PGF's R&D members. The table includes the title of the paper, downloadable PDF file link and the presentation YouTube link. The figure 7 indicate the same.

Figure6: Screenshot of the PGF website developed by Smt. B. Malathi, a PGF member and Research scholar at JNTUH university.

Figure7: The screenshot indicating that the functional approach of PGF cyberpolicing is R&D.

Figure8: The screenshot of webpage - development milestones of PGF.

- iv. Development milestones with the URL for various PGF web devices developed by PGF members, print media, published papers, PPTs, presentations, membership declarations made by the students showing their interest to be the members of PGF. The figure8 is the screenshot of the same. The screenshot in figure9 indicates that the students are interested to become members of PGF and be part of generating awareness among the masses regarding the case study, cyber ethics and impart national consciousness among them. Some requests are sent through Email and others through a handwritten membership declaration in Whats-app groups. The link for PGF Membership Declaration is <https://sites.google.com/site/chandraksekharaiiah/pgf-pairsf/pgf-membership-declaration>. The Link for PGF Requests Sent Through Emails is https://docs.google.com/document/d/1R_o-aNziA5TtbwL0lj0n5T9PnSNGD4TMWnkrLyDcfw/edit?usp=sharing and the Link for PGF Requests Sent through Handwritten Membership Declaration is <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1n1ou7Dt6dHtODODgSyYjsiWVPEL1cpPDQd866eJeGTQ/edit?usp=sharing>.
- v. Committee members and contact details as shown in figure10.

Figure9: The screenshot that indicates the interest of the students to become members of PGF

Figure10: The screenshot of the PGF committee members webpage that show the founder details

- F. Through field research, F. PGF helped mitigate the impact of cybercrime groups. According to PGF, a cybercrime researcher should visit police stations, file complaints against cybercriminal organisations, follow the case's progression through the judicial system, and more. The alternative is academic tedium confined to a laboratory or classroom. Cyberpolicing changes were therefore implemented by PGF via the use of a 360-degree viewpoint. So, PGF used several RTI petitions, got replies, and filed charges against the cybercrimes in the case study. The prior works [1–20] have released photographs and screenshots of the following: submitted FIRs, chargesheets, police complaints, RTI petitions, and their answers.
- G. The PGF is geared at ensuring that students are well-prepared for tests by providing them with information on cybercrimes, cyber ethics, national values, sedition law, and other related topics. The content analysis summary of the pupils' responses to SMI inquiries is used to determine their amazing social media intelligence. All of this is detailed in the article [25]. The article presents a few images that show the answers to the queries, such as the PGF social media account and how it defuses the FGoT [21].

4. PGF's Cyberpolicing through guidance and counselling to students via social media

PGF web devices are linked to social media for performing the PGF's social media campaign. Also, the social media accounts in YouTube and Soundcloud included presentations related to the cyberpolicing case study by the students, research scholars and faculty. A sample of such YouTube account is shown in the figure11. PGF members also used the googleplus account for interacting with students to analyse the national cognition in them. A sample of it is shown in the figure12. The posts and comments in it clearly indicate that students are benefitted by the approach employed by the PGF, its founder and members to educate the students w.r.t the case study,

sedition law, cyber ethics, cyber forensics, cyberpolicing etc.
The

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VM6Z42by9FLXQ1sw3tj5oW1nv8MkFUrb/view?usp=sharing> link is of the document that contains the post and comments in the social network. A sample of those posts are:

- Kankala Sathish-2015-09-14T20:15:39+0000- Updated: 2015-09-14T20:17:08+0000
Regarding 1st mid exam the case study is a different experience. It is helpful for us. Shared to the community [profchandswnsubjectclassgroup](#) - Public
- bassel basrdah-2015-09-14T10:37:35+0000- Updated: 2015-09-14T10:37:35+0000
Regarding 1st mid exam:
this type of case studies necessary for students, regarding cyber crimes
Shared to the community [profchandswnsubjectclassgroup](#) – Public
- Tanmai k-2015-09-15T04:27:25+0000- Updated: 2015-09-15T04:27:25+0000
My view regarding..
-->Mid 1 exam:
It's a great and a very different experience to attempt such an exam that has created awareness and made us to think out of classroom, that is.. the 'Society' today and the Cyber crimes prevailing.
Thank you sir.

Figure 11: Screenshot of a presentations in YouTube account of PGF member

Figure 12: Screenshot of the posts made in the Googleplus account of a

PGF member.

5. Conclusions

Educators play a pivotal role in nation building because it is their job to inculcate a sense of patriotism in their students and give them the tools they need to honour their country's symbols and traditions. That is the true meaning of education. Not to mention how valuable it is to establish academic excellence. Which means that the PGF is comprised of

faculty members and students from a variety of academic programmes at JNTUH-affiliated universities, including research scholars and graduate and undergraduate students. Cyberpolicing in the form of research and development and cyberpolicing in the form of PGF's social media counselling and guidance to students are both covered in this paper. In addition to discussing PGF's accomplishments in defusing and reducing the effects of TBDCOs, the article details the development milestones of PGF. The numerous online gadgets created.

References

1. Usha Gayatri P., and Chandra Sekharaiah K., "Encasing the Baneful Side of Internet", National Conference on Computer Science & Security (COCSS 2013), 5-6 April 2013, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel Institute of Technology, Vasad, Gujarat, India.
2. B.Tirupathi Kumar , K.Chandra Sekharaiah , P.Mounitha, "A Case Study of Web Content Mining in Handling Cybercrime", International Journal of Advanced Research in Science & Engineering, Vol. No. 04, Special Issue (01), September 2015, www.ijarse.com ISSN 2319- 8354.
3. P. Usha Gayatri, K Chandra Sekharaiah, D.Radhika, G.Sruthi, K.Satish, S.Mounika, K.Shravani, Ambuja Kulshreshtha, "Exploring Cyber Intelligence Alternatives for Countering Cyber Crime: A Continuing Case Study for the Nation", Proceedings of the Intl Conf.@Bharati Vidyapeeth's Institute of Computer Applications and Management (BVICAM), New Delhi (INDIA).
4. P. Usha Gayatri, K Chandra Sekharaiah, "A Case Study of Multiple Cybercrimes Against the Union of India", Presented in NCIST'2017@Manipur Institute of Technology, Manipur University & published in International Journal of Computer & Mathematical Sciences IJCMS ISSN 2347 – 8527 Volume 6, Issue 3 March 2017, pp.71-79.
5. G.Aparna, P.Usha Gayatri, Seetha Mounika, D. Radhika, K Chandra Sekharaiah, "Reviewing a Judicial Case Study of Multiple Cybercrimes", in IndiaCOM2016 Intl. Conf., BVICAM, New Delhi, Mar'16.
6. P Usha Gayatri, K. Chandra Sekharaiah, P. premchand "Analytics of Judicial Case Study of Multiple Cyber Crimes against the Union of India" School of Law, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, 2-3 March 2018.
7. S Ravi Kumar, K Chandra Sekharaiah, Y.K Sundara Krishna, M Gouri Shenkar "Cybercrimes-Trends and Challenges in Achieving Swachh Digital India: a Case Study" MRITCISTCSE-2018, ISBN:97893 83038 596, Pg:6-8.
8. S Ravi Kumar, K Chandra Sekharaiah, Y.K Sundara Krishna "Cybercrimes-Trends and Challenges in Achieving Swachh Digital India using a Public Cloud: A Case Study" School of Law, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, 2-3 March 2018.
9. Madan Mohan K., Chandra Sekharaiah K, A Case Study of ICT Solutions against ICT Abuse: An RTI Act 2005 Success Story, National Seminar on S&T for National Development, Manipur Univ., Imphal, Mar'17.
10. N Srihari Rao, K Chandra Sekharaiah and A Ananda Rao "An Approach to Distinguish the Conditions of Flash Crowd versus DDoS Attacks and to remedy a Cyber Crime" School of Law, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, 2-3 March 2018.
11. N.Srihari Rao, K.Chandra Sekharaiah, A.Ananda Rao. (2017) "A Survey of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) Defense Techniques in ISP Domains." In 5th International Conference on Innovations in Computer Science and Engineering (ICICSE-2017).
12. <https://sites.google.com/site/sekharaiahk/apeoples-governanceforumwebpage>
13. K Chandra Sekharaiah, "Impact of the RTI Act within a Public Authority Organization towards EmployeeEmployer Engagement: A Case Study", In proceedings of the Intl. Conf., "ENRICHING EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN ORGANIZATION-ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY", 30Jan-1Feb2015.
14. K. Madan mohan, K Chandra Sekharaiah, P. Premchand "Impact of RTI Act with in Public Authority Organization Toward Employee Employer Engagement: A Case Study" School of Law, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, 2-3 March 2018.

15. Ramesh Babu J, Chandra Sekharaiah K, "Adaptive Management of Cybercriminal, Maladaptive Organizations, in the Offing, that Imperil the Nation" IIT Kharagpur, Mar2018&ICDMAI, Pune,Jan2018.
16. B. Tirupathi Kumar, K Chandra Sekharaiah, D. Suresh Babu "Towards National Integration by Analyzing the Web Mining Results of a Case of Cybercrime", in 2nd Intl. Conf. on Information and Communication Technology for Competitive Strategies (ICTCS-2016) Udaipur, Rajasthan, India, 4-5Mar 2016.
17. Gouri Shankar M. P.UshaGayatri, Niraja S., K Chandra Sekharaiah, "Dealing with Indian Jurisprudence by Analyzing the Web Mining Results of a Case of Cybercrimes", in Procds. of ComNet 2016 International Conference, 20-21 Feb. 2016, Ahmedabad, India.
18. N. Srihari Rao, K. Chandra Sekharaiah, A. Ananda Rao, "Janani Janmabhoomischa Swargaadapi Gareeyasi", BVRIT, International Conference on Research Advancements in Applied Engineering Sciences, Computer and Communication Technologies, (ICRAAESCCT-18), 12-13Jul2018. Conference Proceeding of 3rd International Conference on Research Trends in Engineering, Applied Science and Management (ICRTESSM-2018) Osmania University Campus, Hyderabad, Telangana State, India on 4th November 2018, ISBN: 978-93-87433-44-1 330
19. K. Santhoshi, K. Chandra Sekharaiah, Naga lakshmi Kumari "ICT Based Social Policing for Swatch Digital India" School of Law, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, 2-3 March 2018.
20. K. Madan Mohan, K.Chandra Sekharaiah, N.Santhoshi, "ICT Approach to Defuse the Cybercriminal Sedition Dimension of Telangana Movement", Accepted for publication in International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET), Vol. 7,No. 3.29 (2018).
21. K.Pavana Johar, B.Malathi, S.Ravi Kumar, N.Srihari Rao, K.Madan Mohan, K.Chandra Sekharaiah, "India-abusive Government-of-Telangana (GoT2011): A Constitutional IT (an SMI) Solution", International Journal of Research in Electronics and Computer Engineering(IJRECE) Vol. 6 Issue 3 (July - September 2018) ISSN: 2393-9028 (PRINT) | ISSN: 2348-2281), pp.1118-1124.
22. N.Santhoshi, K.Chandra Sekharaiah, K.Madan Mohan, S.Ravi Kumar, B.Malathi, "Cyberintelligence Alternatives to Offset Online Sedition by in-Website Image Analysis through WebCrawler Cyber forensics", Springer Conf. on Soft Computing and Image Processing, Hyderabad, pp 187-199.
23. B.Malathi K.Chandrasekharaiah GPL Jayasree, "Analytical Trends and Practices of Web Intelligence" , WIR '16 , Pages 121-125 , ACM New York, NY, USA ©2016 , ISBN: 978-1-4503-4278-0
24. B. Malathi, and K. Chandra Sekharaiah, "Web Intelligent Information Systems: A PGF-mediated Social Media Evaluation Perspective", International Journal of Management, Technology And Engineering(IJMTE), Volume 8, Issue XI, NOVEMBER/2018, pp.684-690, ISSN NO : 2249-7455.
- [1] B. Malathi, K. ChandraSekharaiah, "Comparative Evaluation of SMMD Values of Popular Social Media Sites: PGF-A High SMMD Case", Proceedings of the AICTE Sponsored 2nd International Conference on Advances in Computing and Communication Technologies(ICACCT-2019), CMRCET, Hyderabad, 16th-17th December2019, pg.11. & Springer Nature - <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789811579608> pg 721-732) ISBN 978-981-15-7960-8